

Bayesian estimation of ETAS models using Rstan

(applied to seismic recurrence in Ecuador 2016)

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Introduction

There were four mega earthquakes in the Ecuadorian Coast in the past century:

- ▶ 1906(magnitude 8.8)
- ▶ 1942(magnitude 7.8)
- ▶ 1958(magnitude 7.7)
- ▶ 1979(magnitude 8.2)

And then... April 16th, 2016 a quake of magnitude 7.8 according to USGS (magnitude 7.4 according to Seismology Institute - EPN)

Total Intensity with observed points
Circles area proportional to magnitude; red: recent, blu:older

Methods

Omori law

The empirical law of Omori and the law of Omori-Utsu (also called Modified Law of Omori) Utsu1995 describe the decreasing frequency of aftershocks over time after an earthquake:

$$N(t) = \frac{K}{(t + c)} \quad (1)$$

$$N(t) = \frac{K}{(t + c)^p} \quad (2)$$

Where $N(t)$ is the occurrence rate of events, t is the time since the earthquake and K, c, p are constants.

Methods

Gutenberg-Richter law

... relates the magnitude to the number of earthquakes with magnitudes greater than M :

$$\log_{10}N(\geq M) = a - bM \quad (3)$$

That is, the number of events of magnitude greater than a threshold, decreases exponentially with the increase of that threshold value by a power law.

So, the distribution of magnitudes by the Gutenberg-Richter law

$$s(m) = \beta e^{-\beta m}$$

Gutenberg-Richter law

Gutenberg-Richter law: linear regression $\log(N) = a + bM$ and then $a = 5.064(sd = 0.039)$ and $-0.694(sd = 0.007)$. From these values, b is 0.694 and $\beta = b \ln(10) = 1.598$.

Number of events with magnitude greater than

Log base 10 of number of events with magnitude greater than

Methods

An earthquake T is represented by a tuple (x_i, y_i, z_i, M_i)

Temporal ETAS model

The simplest ETAS model is the temporal model with constant

background seismicity: $\lambda(t|H_t) = \mu + \sum_{j:t_j < t} \frac{K(p-1)c^{p-1}}{(t-t_j+c)^p}$

where μ is the background intensity that is assumed to be constant (measured in events / day) and

$$g(t) = \frac{(p-1)c^{p-1}}{(t+c)^p} \quad (4)$$

is the probability density function of the occurrence times of the events triggered by previous earthquakes.

Methods

Temporal ETAS model

If the background intensity is not constant, but depends only on the longitude and latitude x, y we have:

$$\lambda(t|H_t) = \mu(x, y) + \sum_{j:t_j < t} \frac{K(p-1)c^{p-1}}{(t-t_j+c)^p}$$

where $\mu(x, y)$ is now measured in events per day per unit of longitude and per unit of latitude. In this case, it is generally assumed that $\mu(x, y) = \mu u(x, y)$ where μ on the right side is a constant.

Methods

ETAS model with magnitudes

Considering the magnitudes of earthquakes we have the model

$$\lambda(t|H_t) = \mu + \sum_{j:t_j < t} \frac{K(p-1)c^{p-1}Ae^{\alpha(M_j - M_0)}}{(t - t_j + c)^p}$$

Methods

ETAS models stability

The event rate in the ETAS models may explode. Stability depends on the branching ratio n = expected number of descendants of a parent event. We have

$$n = \int_0^\infty dt \int_{M_0}^{M_{max}} s(m) \lambda(t) dm$$

with $s(m) = \beta e^{-\beta m}$ the distribution of magnitudes by the Gutenberg-Richter law and $\lambda(t)$ the branching term.

For the temporal ETAS model with magnitudes and $p > 1$ we have

$$n = \frac{Kc^{1-p}\beta}{(p-1)(\beta-\alpha)} \frac{1 - e^{-(\beta-\alpha)(M_{max}-M_0)}}{1 - e^{-\beta(M_{max}-M_0)}}$$

Methods

For the temporal ETAS model with magnitudes and $p > 1$ we have

$$n = \frac{Kc^{1-p}\beta}{(p-1)(\beta-\alpha)} \frac{1-e^{-(\beta-\alpha)(M_{max}-M_0)}}{1-e^{-\beta(M_{max}-M_0)}} \text{ Assuming } M_{max} = \infty \text{ the}$$

previous formula can be reduced to: $n = \frac{Kc^{1-p}\beta}{(p-1)(\beta-\alpha)}$

Sornette2005 y Touati2011

and n is infinite if $p < 1$ or if $\alpha > \beta$.

Methods

ETAS models stability

If each event induces another event: $n = 1$ then the process propagates indefinitely. This justifies normalizing the functions that appear in the sum over the preceding events. For example $\int_0^\infty \frac{K}{(t+c)^p} dt = 1$ implies that we need to add $(p-1)c^{p-1}$ to the constant K and similarly $\int_{M_0}^{M_{max}} \beta e^{-\beta(m)} dm = 1$ implies we need to add $1/(\exp(-\beta M_0) - \exp(-\beta M_{max}))$ to the constant β .

Methods

For temporal models: $\log L(\theta) = \sum_j \log \lambda(t_j | H_t) - \int_0^{T_{max}} \lambda(t) dt$

The closed forms for temporal and temporal with magnitudes

models: $\log L(\mu, k, p, c) =$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \log(\lambda(t_i)) - \mu T_{max} - k \sum_{i=1}^N \left(1 - \frac{c^{p-1}}{(T_{max} - t_i + c)^{p-1}}\right)$$

$$\log L(\mu, k, p, c, A, \alpha) = \sum_{i=1}^N \log(\lambda(t_i)) - \mu T_{max} -$$

$$kA \sum_{i=1}^N e^{\alpha(M_i - M_0)} \left(1 - \frac{c^{p-1}}{(T_{max} - t_i + c)^{p-1}}\right)$$

Listing 1: Temporal Rstan model with constant background seismicity

```
1  functions{
2    real loglikelihood(int N,
3                      real mu,
4                      real k,
5                      real p,
6                      real c,
7                      vector times_diff,
8                      real tmax){
9    real seismic_rate[N];
10   real integral_of_rate[N];
11   real integral_mu;
12   real log_likelihood;
13   seismic_rate[N]=log(mu);
14   integral_of_rate[N]=0;
15   for(j in 1:(N-1)){
16     vector[N-j] y;
17     int start;
18     int end;
19     start =N*(j-1)-(j*(j-1))/2 + 1;
20     end =j*N-(j*(j+1))/2;
21     y=times_diff[start:end];
22     y=(k*(p-1) * c^(p-1))*exp(-p*
23       log(y+c));
24     seismic_rate[j]=log(mu+sum(y));
25   }
26
27   integral_mu=mu*tmax;
28   log_likelihood=sum(seismic_rate)-
29     integral_mu-sum(integral_of_rate);
30   return(log_likelihood);
31 }
32
33 data{
34   int<lower=0> N;
35   real<lower=0> max_time;
36   vector[N*(N-1)/2] times_diff;
37 }
38
39 parameters{
40   real<lower=0> mu;
41   real<lower=0> k;
42   real<lower=1.000005> p;
43   real<lower=0.00005> c;
44 }
45
46 model{
47   mu~exponential(2.8);
48   k~exponential(2.8);
49   p~exponential(0.3);
50   c~exponential(2.8);
51   increment_log_prob(loglikelihood(N,mu,
52     k,
53     p,c,times_diff,max_time));
54 }
```

Listing 2: Temporal with magnitudes Rstan model with constant background seismicity

```
1  functions{
2    real loglikelihood(int N,
3                      real mu,
4                      real k,
5                      real p,
6                      real c,
7                      real alpha,
8                      real A,
9                      vector t,
10                     vector magnitudes,
11                     vector times_diff,
12                     real max_time,
13                     real magnitude0)
14    real seismic_rate[N];
15    real integral_of_rate[N];
16    real integral_mu;
17    real log_likelihood;
18    seismic_rate[N]= log(mu);
19    integral_of_rate[N]=0;
20    for(j in 1:(N-1)){
21      vector[N-j] y;
22      int start;
23      int end;
24      start = N*(j - 1)-(j*(j-1))/2 +
25            1;
26      end =j*N-(j*(j+1))/2;
27      y=times_diff[start:end];
28      y=(k*A*(p-1)*c^(p-1))*exp(alpha
          (magnitudes[(j+1):]-
          magnitude0))
          .*exp(-p*log(y+c));
          seismic_rate[j]=log(mu+sum(y));
          integral_of_rate[j]=(k*A)*exp(
            alpha*
            (magnitudes[j+1]-
            magnitude0))*(1-c^(p-1)/
            ((times_diff[j]+c)^(p-1)));
          }
          integral_mu =mu*max_time;
          log_likelihood=sum(seismic_rate)-
          integral_mu-sum(integral_of_rate
            );
          return(log_likelihood);
        }
      }
    data{
      int<lower=0> N;
      vector[N] times;
      real<lower=0> max_time;
      vector[N] magnitudes;
      vector[N*(N-1)/2] times_diff;
      real<lower=0> threshold_magnitude;
    }
    parameters{
      real<lower=0> mu;
      real<lower=0> k;
      real<lower=1.000005> p;
      real<lower=0.00005> c;
      real<lower=0> alpha;
      real<lower=0> A;
    }
    model{
      mu~exponential(2.8);
      k~exponential(2.8);
      p~exponential(0.3);
      c~exponential(2.8);
      alpha~exponential(2.8);
    }
  }
```

```
64 A~exponential(2.8);
65 increment_log_prob(loglikelihood(N, 67      , max_time, threshold_magnitude));
      mu, k, p, c      68 }
66 , alpha, A, times, magnitudes, times_diff
```

Methods

Isotropic spatio temporal ETAS model

In 1998 Ogata proposed a modified version of the spatio-temporal ETAS model:

$$\lambda(t, x, y) = \mu + \sum_{j:t_j < t} g(t - t_j, x - x_j, y - y_j, M_j | H_t)$$

where

$g(t, x, y, M) \frac{Ke^{\alpha(M-M_0)}}{(t+c)^p} \left\{ \frac{x^2+y^2}{e^{\gamma(M-M_0)}} + d \right\}^{-q}$ and the background intensity μ is constant. We can normalize:

$$g(t, x, y, M) = \frac{K(p-1)c^{p-1}(q-1)d^{q-1}\alpha e^{(\alpha-\gamma)(M-M_0)}}{\pi(t+c)^p} \left\{ \frac{x^2+y^2}{e^{\gamma(M-M_0)}} + d \right\}^{-q}$$

Methods

Anisotropic spatio temporal ETAS model

$$\lambda(t, x, y) = \mu + \sum_{j:t_j < t} g(t - t_j, x - x_j, y - y_j, M_j | H_t)$$

$$\text{where } g(t, x, y, M) = \frac{Ke^{\alpha(M-M_0)}}{(t+c)^p} \left\{ \frac{pS_j p^T}{e^{\alpha(M_j-M_0)}} + d \right\}^{-q}$$

and $p = (x - x_j, y - y_j)$ is a row vector, x_j, y_j are the coordinates of the earthquake j preceding the earthquake with epicenter x, y (both in the same cluster) and S_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots$) are positive definite symmetric matrices representing the normalized covariance matrix of the earthquake cluster obtained by applying MBC or Magnitude Based Cluster algorithm

**Cluster of earthquakes
Manabi-Esmeraldas**

**Cluster earthquakes Manabi- Esmeraldas
09/04/2016-16/07/2016**

Methods

Magnitude Based Cluster MBC

This method is based on selecting the greatest magnitude earthquake (with magnitude M_j) between those that are not in any cluster yet (if there are two with equal magnitude the oldest one is chosen) and then the earthquakes of the cluster associated with the previous selected earthquake, are those with latitude and longitude $\pm 3.33 * 10^{0.5M_j-2}$ km (Utsu spatial distance) from the latitude and longitude of the selected earthquake and with a time difference therefrom (towards the future) of $\max(100, 10^{0.5M_j-1})$ days Ogata1998. Then the process is repeated with earthquakes that are not yet in any cluster until all earthquakes belong to a cluster.

Bivariate normal distribution

For the anisotropic model, four normal bivariate models

$$\text{Ogata1998: } N\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ y_1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{\sigma}^2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$$

$$N\left(\begin{pmatrix} \bar{x} \\ \bar{y} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\sigma}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\sigma}^2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$$

$$N\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ y_1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_1^2 & \tilde{\rho}\tilde{\sigma}_1\tilde{\sigma}_2 \\ \tilde{\rho}\tilde{\sigma}_1\tilde{\sigma}_2 & \tilde{\sigma}_2^2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$$

$$N\left(\begin{pmatrix} \bar{x} \\ \bar{y} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\sigma}_1^2 & \hat{\rho}\hat{\sigma}_1\hat{\sigma}_2 \\ \hat{\rho}\hat{\sigma}_1\hat{\sigma}_2 & \hat{\sigma}_2^2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$$

$$N\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ y_1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_1^2 & \tilde{\rho}\tilde{\sigma}_1\tilde{\sigma}_2 \\ \tilde{\rho}\tilde{\sigma}_1\tilde{\sigma}_2 & \tilde{\sigma}_2^2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$$

$$N\left(\begin{pmatrix} \bar{x} \\ \bar{y} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\sigma}_1^2 & \hat{\rho}\hat{\sigma}_1\hat{\sigma}_2 \\ \hat{\rho}\hat{\sigma}_1\hat{\sigma}_2 & \hat{\sigma}_2^2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$$

where (x_1, y_1) is the position of the cluster's main earthquake,
 (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) and centroid of the cluster.

(Ogata 1998)

Bivariate normal distribution

$$\text{And } \tilde{\sigma}^2 = [\sum_j (x_j - x_1)^2 + \sum_j (y_j - y_1)^2] / (2n)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = [\sum_j (x_j - \bar{x})^2 + \sum_j (y_j - \bar{y})^2] / (2n)$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_1^2 = [\sum_j (x_j - x_1)^2] / n \quad \tilde{\sigma}_2^2 = [\sum_j (y_j - y_1)^2] / n$$

$$\tilde{\rho} = [\sum_j (x_j - x_1)(y_j - y_1)] / (n\tilde{\sigma}_1\tilde{\sigma}_2)$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_1^2 = [\sum_j (x_j - x_1)^2] / n$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_2^2 = [\sum_j (y_j - y_1)^2] / n \quad \tilde{\rho} = [\sum_j (x_j - x_1)(y_j - y_1)] / (n\tilde{\sigma}_1\tilde{\sigma}_2)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_1^2 = [\sum_j (x_j - \bar{x})^2] / n$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_2^2 = [\sum_j (y_j - \bar{y})^2] / n$$

$$\hat{\rho} = [\sum_j (x_j - \bar{x})(y_j - \bar{y})] / (n\hat{\sigma}_1\hat{\sigma}_2)$$

(Ogata 1998)

Methods

Bivariate normal

We select the model with the lowest $AIC = -n \ln(\det(S)) + 2k$ where S is the variance covariance matrix for each of the four models and k is the corresponding number of parameters. Ogata1998.

Then the selected matrix is normalized:

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\rho^2}}\right) \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_2/\sigma_1 & -\rho \\ -\rho & \sigma_1/\sigma_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Methods

Hypocentral ETAS model

Guo2015 introduces a modification of the spatio temporal ETAS model that includes the depths of earthquakes

$$\lambda(t, x, y) = \mu + \sum_{j:t_j < t} g(t - t_j, x - x_j, y - y_j, M_j | H_t)$$

where $g(t, x, y, M) = \frac{Ke^{\alpha(M-M_0)}}{(t+c)^p} \left\{ \frac{pS_j p^T}{e^{\alpha(M_j-M_0)}} + d \right\}^{-q} h(z - z_i, z_i)$ and

$$h(z, z') = \frac{\left(\frac{z}{Z}\right)^\eta \frac{z'}{Z} \left(1 - \frac{z}{Z}\right)^{\eta(1 - \frac{z'}{Z})}}{ZB\left(\eta \frac{z'}{Z} + 1, \eta\left(1 - \frac{z}{Z}\right) + 1\right)}$$

with Z the thickness of the seismogenic layer and

$B(p, q) = \int_0^1 t^{p-1} (1-t)^{q-1}$ is the Beta function.

Methods

For spatio temporal models

$$\log L(\theta) = \sum_j \log \lambda(t_j, x_j, y_j | H_t) - \int_0^{T_{max}} \int \int_S \lambda(t, x, y) dx dy dt$$

For the hypocentral ETAS model, the logarithm of the likelihood is

$$\log L(\theta) = \sum_j \log \lambda(t_j, x_j, y_j | H_t) - \int_0^{T_{max}} \int \int_S \int_0^Z \lambda(t, x, y) dz dx dy dt$$

In spatio temporals models, the log likelihood does not have a closed form.

Methods

We approximate the log likelihood for spatio temporal models using polar coordinates and S the minimum covering circle

Minimum Covering Circle Welzl 1991

Methods(Cont)

Approximation

$$\begin{aligned} & \log L(\mu, k, p, c, d, \alpha, \gamma) \\ & \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \log(\lambda(t_i)) - \mu T_{max} \pi r^2 - \\ & k \alpha \sum_{i=1}^N e^{\alpha(M_i - M_0)} \left(1 - \frac{c^{p-1}}{(T_{max} - t_i + c)^{p-1}}\right) \left(1 - \frac{d^{q-1}}{\left(\frac{r_i^2}{e^{\alpha(M_i - M_0)}} + d\right)^{q-1}}\right) \end{aligned}$$

where r is the radius of the minimum covering circle, r_i is the greatest distance between earthquake i and the previous earthquakes according to the metric defined in the cluster.

Methods

For the anisotropic model, the Euclidean distance is changed by the metric defined by the standardized variance covariance matrix S_j where now r_i is calculated as the maximum distance (according to the previous metric) between each earthquake and the previous earthquakes in the cluster.

Methods

Pre-processing

We sorted the data in reverse chronological time and calculated the time, latitude, and longitude differences for each earthquake j for which we know the initial and final positions where the differences of its time, latitude, and longitude with respect to the previous earthquakes are:

$$start = N * (j - 1) - (j * (j - 1))/2 + 1$$

$$end = j * N - (j * (j + 1))/2$$

Listing 3: Anisotropic spatio-temporal Rstan model with constant background seismicity

```

1  functions{
2    real loglikelihood(int N,
3                      real mu,
4                      real k,
5                      real p,
6                      real c,
7                      real q,
8                      real d,
9                      real alpha,
10   real gamma,
11   vector t,
12   vector magnitudes,
13   vector times_diff,
14   vector latitudes,
15   vector longitudes,
16   vector quadratic_factorAni,
17   vector quadratic_factorIso,
18   real tmax,
19   real magnitude0,
20   real lat_min,
21   real lat_max,
22   real long_min,
23   real long_max,
24   real radius
25 ){
26   real seismic_rate[N];
27   real integral_of_rate[N];
28   real integral_mu;
29   real log_likelihood;
30   seismic_rate[N]=log(mu);
31   integral_of_rate[N]=0;
32   for(j in 1:(N-1)){
33     vector[N-j] y;
34     vector[N-j] z;
35     vector[N-1] x;
36     real temp;
37     real temp1;
38     real temp2;
39     int start;
40     int end;
41     start =N*(j-1)-(j*(j-1))/2 + 1;
42     end =j*N-(j*(j+1))/2;
43     y=times_diff[start:end];
44     z=exp(-q*log(quadratic_factorAni
45               [start:end]./
46               (exp(gamma*(magnitudes[(j+1):-
47                 magnitude0]))+d));
48     y=(k*alpha*(p-1)*c^(p-1)*(q-1)*d
49        ^((q-1)*(1/pi)))
50     *exp((alpha-gamma)*(magnitudes
51               [(j+1):-
52                 magnitude0))
53     .*exp(-p*log(y+c)));
54     y=y .* z;
55     seismic_rate[j]=log(mu+sum(y));
56     temp=exp(alpha*(magnitudes[j+1]-
57               magnitude0));
58     temp1=exp(gamma*(magnitudes[j
59               +1]-magnitude0));
60     temp2=max(quadratic_factorAni[
61               start:end]);
62     integral_of_rate[j]=k*alpha*temp

```

```

56      *(1-c^(p-1)/      82
      ((times_diff[j]+c)^(p-1)))*(1-83
      ^((q-1)/      84
      ((temp2/(temp1)+d)^(q-1))); 85
58    }      86
59    integral_mu=mu*tmax*pi()*radius^287
60    log_likelihood=sum(seismic_rate)-88
61    integral_mu-sum(integral_of_rat89
      ); 90
62    return(log_likelihood); 91
63  } 92
64 } 93
65 data{ 94
66   int<lower=0> N; 95
67   vector[N] times; 96
68   real<lower=0> max_time; 97
69   vector[N] magnitudes; 98
70   vector[N*(N-1)/2] 99
      quadratic_factorAni; 100
71   vector[N*(N-1)/2] 101
      quadratic_factorIso; 102
72   vector[N*(N-1)/2] times_diff; 103
73   real<lower=0> threshold_magnitude; 104
74   vector[N] latitudes; 105
75   vector[N] longitudes; 106
76   real lat_min; 107
77   real lat_max; 108
78   real long_min; 109
79   real long_max; 110
80   real<lower=0> radius; 111
81 }

```

```

parameters{
  real<lower=0> mu;
  real<lower=0> k;
  real<lower=1.000005> p;
  real<lower=0> c;
  real<lower=0> d;
  real<lower=1.00005> q;
  real<lower=0> alpha;
  real<lower=0> gamma;
}

model{
  mu~exponential(2.8);
  k~exponential(2.8);
  p~exponential(2.8);
  c~exponential(2.8);
  d~exponential(2.8);
  q~exponential(2.8);
  gamma~exponential(2.8);
  alpha~gamma~exponential(5);
  increment_log_prob(loglikelihood(N,
    mu,k,p,c,q,d,
    alpha,gamma,times,magnitudes,
    times_diff,
    latitudes,longitudes,
    quadratic_factorAni,
    quadratic_factorIso,max_time,
    threshold_magnitude,
    lat_min,lat_max,long_min,long_max,
    radius));
}

```

Listing 4: Anisotropic spatial-temporal hypocentral Rstan model with constant background seismicity

```

1  functions{
2      real loglikelihood(int N,
3                          real mu,
4                          real k,
5                          real p,
6                          real c,
7                          real q,
8                          real d,
9                          real alpha,
10                         real gamma,
11                         real eta,
12                         vector t,
13                         vector magnitudes,
14                         vector times_diff,
15                         vector depths_diff,
16                         vector latitudes,
17                         vector longitudes,
18                         vector depths,
19                         vector quadratic_factorAni,
20                         vector quadratic_factorIso,
21                         real tmax,
22                         real magnitude0,
23                         real lat_min,
24                         real lat_max,
25                         real long_min,
26                         real long_max,
27                         real radius,
28                         real layer_depth
29                     ){
30
31     real seismic_rate[N];
32     real integral_of_rate[N];
33     real integral_mu;
34     real log_likelihood;
35     seismic_rate[N]=log(mu);
36     integral_of_rate[N]=0;
37     for(j in 1:(N-1)){
38         vector[N-j] y;
39         vector[N-j] z;
40         vector[N-j] x;
41         vector[N-j] w;
42         real temp;
43         real temp1;
44         real temp2;
45         real temp3;
46         int start;
47         int end;
48         start =N*(j-1)-(j*(j-1))/2 + 1;
49         end =j*N-(j*(j+1))/2;
50         y=times_diff[start:end];
51         z=exp(-q*log(quadratic_factorAni[
52             start:end]
53             ./ (exp(gamma*(magnitudes[(j+1):]
54                 -
55                 magnitude0))+d));
56         y=(k*alpha*(p-1)*c^(p-1)*(q-1)*d
57             ^ (q-1)*
58             (1/pi()))*exp((alpha-gamma)*
59             (magnitudes[(j+1):]-magnitude0

```

```

    ))
57     .* exp(-p*log(y+c));
58     x=y .* z ;
59     z=(1/layer_depth) *
60     depths_diff[start:end];
61     y=(1/layer_depth) *
62     depths[(j+1):N];
63     for(i in 1:(N-j)){
64         w[i]=(1/(layer_depth * exp(
65             lbeta(eta *
66                 ( y[i] + 1, eta - eta * ( y[
67                     i] + 1)))) *
68                 (z[i] ^ (eta * (y[i]))) *
69                 ((1 - z[i]) ^
70                 (eta-eta * ( y[i]))));
71         seismic_rate[j]=log(mu+sum(x .*
72             w));
73         temp=exp(alpha*(magnitudes[j+1]-
74             magnitude0));
75         temp1=exp(gamma*(magnitudes[j
76             +1]-magnitude0));
77         temp2=max(quadratic_factorAni[
78             start:end]);
79         integral_of_rate[j]=k*alpha*temp
80             *(1-c^(p-1))
81             /(((times_diff[j]+c)^(p-1))*
82             d^(q-1)
83             /(((temp2/(temp1)+d)^(q-1)));
84     }
85     integral_mu=mu*tmax*pi()*
86     layer_depth*
87     (radius^2);
88     log_likelihood=sum(seismic_rate)-
89     integral_mu-sum(integral_of_rate);
90     return(log_likelihood);
91 }
92
93 data{
94     int<lower=0> N;
95     vector[N] times;
96     real<lower=0> max_time;
97     vector[N] magnitudes;
98     vector[N*(N-1)/2]
99     quadratic_factorAni;
100    vector[N*(N-1)/2]
101    quadratic_factorIso;
102    vector[N*(N-1)/2] times_diff;
103    vector[N*(N-1)/2] depths_diff;
104    real<lower=0> threshold_magnitude;
105    vector[N] latitudes;
106    vector[N] longitudes;
107    vector[N] depths;
108    real lat_min;
109    real lat_max;
110    real long_min;
111    real long_max;
112    real<lower=0> radius;
113    real<lower=0> layer_depth;
114 }
115
116 parameters{
117     real<lower=0> mu;
118     real<lower=0> k;
119     real<lower=1.000005> p;
120     real<lower=0> c;
121     real<lower=0> d;
122     real<lower=1.00005> q;
123     real<lower=0> alpha;
124     real<lower=0> gamma;
125     real<lower=0> eta;
126 }
127
128 model{
129     mu~exponential(2);

```

```

117 k~exponential(2);           126 alpha ,gamma,eta ,times ,magnitudes ,
118 p~exponential(2);           times_diff ,
119 c~exponential(2);           127 depths_diff ,latitudes ,longitudes ,
120 d~exponential(2);           128 depths ,quadratic_factorAni ,
121 q~exponential(2);           129 quadratic_factorIso ,max_time ,
122 eta~exponential(2);         130 threshold_magnitude ,lat_min ,
123 gamma~exponential(2);       lat_max ,long_min ,
124 alpha~gamma~exponential(5); 131 long_max ,radius ,layer_depth));
125 increment_log_prob(loglikelihood(N,132 }
      mu,k,p,c,q,d,

```

Listing 5: Anisotropic Rstar model with variable background seismicity

```

1  functions{
2  real loglikelihood(int N,
3                      real mu,
4                      real k,
5                      real p,
6                      real c,
7                      real q,
8                      real d,
9                      real alpha,
10                     real gamma,
11                     vector t,
12                     vector magnitudes,
13                     vector times_diff,
14                     vector latitudes,
15                     vector longitudes,
16                     vector
17                     background_seismic_rates
18                     ,
19                     vector
20                     quadratic_factorAni
21                     ,
22                     vector
23                     quadratic_factorIso
24                     ,
25                     real tmax,
26                     real magnitude0,
27                     real lat_min,
28                     real lat_max,
29                     real long_min,
30                     real long_max,
31                     real radius
32                 ){
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+1]-magnitude0)); 83
temp2=max(quadratic_factorAni[ 84
start:end]); 85
57 integral_of_rate[j]=k*alpha*temp2 86
*(1-c^(p-1)/ 87
((times_diff[j]+c)^(p-1)))* 88
58 (1-d^(q-1)/((temp2/(temp1)+d)^(q-1))); 89
60 } 90
61 integral_mu=mu*sum( 91
background_seismic_rates)* 92
62 tmax*pi()*radius^2; 93
63 log_likelihood=sum(seismic_rate)- 94
64 integral_mu-sum(integral_of_rate); 95
65 return(log_likelihood); 96
66 } 97
67 } 98
68 data{ 99
69 int<lower=0> N; 100
70 vector[N] times; 101
71 real<lower=0> max_time; 102
72 vector[N] magnitudes; 103
73 vector[N*(N-1)/2] 104
quadratic_factorAni; 105
74 vector[N*(N-1)/2] 106
quadratic_factorIso; 107
75 vector[N*(N-1)/2] times_diff; 108
76 real<lower=0> threshold_magnitude; 109
77 vector[N] latitudes; 110
78 vector[N] longitudes; 109
79 vector[N] background_seismic_rates; 110
80 real lat_min;
81 real lat_max; 111
82 real long_min;
real long_max;
real<lower=0> radius;
}
parameters{
real<lower=0> mu;
real<lower=0> k;
real<lower=1.000005> p;
real<lower=0> c;
real<lower=0> d;
real<lower=1.00005> q;
real<lower=0> alpha;
real<lower=0> gamma;
}
model{
mu~exponential(2.8);
k~exponential(2.8);
p~exponential(2.8);
c~exponential(2.8);
d~exponential(2.8);
q~exponential(2.8);
gamma~exponential(2.8);
alpha-gamma~exponential(5);
increment_log_prob(loglikelihood(N,
mu,k,p,c,q,d,
alpha,gamma,times,magnitudes,
times_diff,
latitudes,longitudes,
background_seismic_rates,
quadratic_factorAni,
quadratic_factorIso,
max_time,threshold_magnitude,
lat_min,lat_max,long_min,long_max,
radius));
}

```

Methods

We can estimate the probability that a given event is spontaneous or is triggered by others

Kagan1980Zhuang2002. The contribution of the spontaneous seismicity rate to the occurrence of an event i can be taken as the probability that the event i is spontaneousZhuang2008:

$$\phi(i) = \frac{\mu(x_i, y_i)}{\lambda(t_i, x_i, y_i)}$$

Similarly, the probability that the event j is produced by the event i is $\rho_{ij} = \frac{\kappa(M)g(t_j - t_i)f(x_j - x_i, y_j - y_i, m_i)}{\lambda(t_i, x_i, y_i)}$

We can also obtain the expected number of direct aftershocks from the earthquake i as $\sum_j \rho_{ij}$ Zhuang2008

Methods

Inter-event times

The probability density function of the recurrence times (time between two successive events) τ

$$H(\tau) \approx \lambda f(\lambda\tau)$$

where the function $f(x)$ has been found practically the same in different regions and λ is the average rate of events observed in the analyzed region. Saichev2007

The scaling factor of times between earthquakes is taken as the inverse of its mean.

The form of the function $f(x)$ which is demonstrated in Saichev2007 is

$$f(x) = (n\epsilon^\theta x^{-1-\theta} + [1 - n + n\epsilon^\theta x^{-\theta}]^2) * \varphi(x, \epsilon)$$

Table 1: Earthquake distribution in Ecuador 18/03/2016-16/07/2016

Closest province	March	April	May	June	July	Total
Azuay			1			1
Bolivar		4				4
Canar	1	4				5
Carchi	1	1				2
Cotopaxi	1	1				2
El Oro	2	3	4	2		11
Esmeraldas		171	47	16	35	269
Galapagos		3				3
Guayas		3	5			8
Imbabura	1	1				2
Loja	1	3	1	1		6
Los Rios		1		1		2
Manabi	1	399	92	27	22	541
Los Rios		1		1		2
Morona Santiago		6	7	2	1	16
Napo		1	1			2
Pastaza		4	1	1		6
Pichincha	2	5				7
Santa Elena		3	3	1		7
Sto Domingo de los Tsachilas		4				4
Tungurahua		5	1			6
Zamora Chinchipe		2	2			4
Total	10	624	165	51	58	908

Earthquake magnitudes 09/04/2016-16/07/2016

:kground seismicity raclustering coefficient

Background Intensity

Triggered Intensity

Total Intensity

Total Intensity with observed points
Circles area proportional to magnitude; red: recent, blu:older

**Standardized differences between
theoretical and observed frequency (whole model)**

**Standardized differences between
theoretical and observed frequency (background only)**

Results

Anisotropic Distribution

The covariance matrix for the cluster associated with the April 16th big earthquake (804 earthquakes in the cluster) is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1.469 & -0.696 \\ -0.696 & 0.709 \end{pmatrix}$$

and corresponds to the fourth bivariate model fitted.

Table 12: Etas models comparison

Etas Model	ln(L)	Int. 95% ln(L)		# param.	AIC	int.95% AIC	
Temp. sis. cst	1790.7	1787.3	1792.8	4	-3573.5	-3577.6	-3566.5
Temp. seis. var.	1773.3	1769.7	1775.0	4	-3538.6	-3542.0	-3531.4
Magn. seis. cst	1832.8	1689.2	1842.8	6	-3653.7	-3673.7	-3366.5
Magn. seis. var.	1800.8	1797.4	1802.9	6	-3589.5	-3593.8	-3582.7
Spa. temp. iso. seis. cst	1394.4	1387.4	1398.1	8	-2772.7	-2780.1	-2758.7
Spa. temp. ani. seis. cst	1857.1	1852.7	1859.6	8	-3698.3	-3703.2	-3689.4
Spa. temp. ani. seis. var.	1799.9	1794.6	1801.9	8	-3583.8	-3936.8	-3573.3
Hypo. ani. seis. cst.	1974.1	1969.4	1977.0	9	-3930.2	-3936.1	-3920.8
Hypo. ani. seis. var.	1923.3.1	1919.4	1926.1	9	-3828.6	-3834.2	-3821.4

Results

Kernel bivariate density

Kernel bivariate density using the R package kde.

Bivariate kernel density 09/04/2016-16/07/2016

Priors

Weakly informative priors

For the ETAS parameters (must be positive) we used exponential priors and for p and q we use a minimum value close to 1:1.000005.

The radius of the minimum covering circle using Welzl algorithm was, $r = 1.70479$.

Results

Figure: Chains for anisotropic ETAS model with constant background seismicity

Figure: *A posteriori* parameter distributions for anisotropic ETAS model with constant background seismicity

Results

Figure: Correlation of parameter values in the chains for anisotropic ETAS model with constant background seismicity

Figure: Correlation of parameter values in the chains for anisotropic ETAS model with constant background seismicity

Results

Residuals

Temporal ETAS(constant background seismicity)

Figure: Accumulated number of events for temporal Etas model with constant background seismicity

Residuals temporal ETAS(constant background seismicity)

Figure: Residuals for Etas temporal temporal Etas model with constant background seismicity

Temporal ETAS(variable background seismicity)

Figure: Accumulated number of events for temporal ETAS model with variable background seismicity

Residuals temporal ETAS (variable background seismicity)

Figure: Residuals for temporal ETAS model with variable background seismicity

Temporal ETAS: constant vs variable background seismicity)

Figure: Accumulated number of events for temporal ETAS model with constant background seismicity vs variable background seismicity

Residuals temporal ETAS: constant vs variable background seismicity

Figure: Residuals for temporal ETAS model with constant background seismicity vs variable background seismicity

Temporal ETAS with magnitudes and constant background seismicity

Figure: Accumulated number of events for temporal ETAS with magnitudes model and constant background seismicity

Temporal ETAS with magnitudes and constant background seismicity

Figure: Residuals for temporal ETAS with magnitudes model and constant background seismicity

Figure: Accumulated number of events for spatio temporal anisotropic ETAS model and variable background seismicity

Figure: Residuals for spatio temporal anisotropic ETAS model and variable background seismicity

Results

Parent earthquakes

95% credibility intervals for the index of the most probable parent earthquake with 1000 draws from the posterior distributions.

The green line is the big earthquake on April 16 and blue points are the medians of the credibility intervals using the anisotropic spatio temporal model with variable background seismicity.

Confidence intervals for indexes of most probable precursor event

Probability of being background earthquake 16/07/2016-11/09/2017

Probability of being spontaneous earthquake 13/04/2016-16/07/2016

**Induced seismic rate
16/07/2016-11/09/2016**

Inter-event times 18/03/2016-16/07/2016

Rescaled inter-event time

Inter-event times 18/03/2016-16/07/2016

Thanks